

Enhancing Speaking Proficiency through AI-Based Tools: An Experimental Study of English Language Learners at Higher Secondary Level

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Abstract

This study investigates the effect of Artificial Intelligence (AI)-based tools on improvement of speaking proficiency of English language learners in real-time situations. Nowadays, AI-based applications have become game changer by motivating learners and facilitating interactive language acquiring activities in learning contexts. This study was conducted with 120 students of higher secondary level of six different colleges in district Gujrat learning English as compulsory subject. These students were randomly assigned to either an experimental group using AI-supported application TalkPal-AI or a control group receiving traditional instructions. Pre- and post-tests were conducted to assess the students' English-speaking capacities and self-learning abilities, utilizing the smalltalk2.me, which involves variety of speaking guidelines, focused mock practices, pronunciation assessment, and a speech evaluation tool. The results expressed that the experimental group showed significant improvements in speaking skill components e.g. fluency, grammar, pronunciation, Interaction and vocabulary compared to the control group. The findings suggest that AI-based applications effectively heighten English language speaking skills among ESL students and improves their learning processes. These results expresses that AI technology possess high capacity to increase language learning experiences and promote learners' independent urge to acquire learning of languages.

INTRODUCTION

Language plays an important role in global communications. Although all language skills are highly important, learners face hardships in speaking. They found pronunciation and accent to be the most difficult. Communication skills refer to the personal capacity to use any particular language effectively in both written and spoken forms (Claned, 2024). In the four communication skills, productivity is associated with the two major skills of listening and speaking, as they require more attention and focus.

In previous years, education through electronic gadgets has become the centre of attention because it is flexible, wearable, unbiased, and customised (Muhammad et al., 2025b; Safdar et al., 2025). This approach satisfies the unique demands of learners through individual content creation and practice (Anwar et al., 2022; Sharjeel et al., 2022). E-learning provides rapid feedback to individuals. It creates anxiety-free situations and stress-free conditions that do not pressurise and reduce intelligence levels. It enhances comfort and improves the intelligence. It can be widely analysed and interpreted that the adaptive system of learning in this AI-supported era can facilitate decision-making, learning involvement, and focused feedback (Lumenalta, 2025).

If we investigate the educational context, the importance of language learning and the role of information technology are interlinked. Language acquisition is important for global, international, intercultural and cognitive development. Proficiency in more than one language is highly appreciated worldwide. Multilingual skills are encouraged in the academic, personal, and professional domains. In this regard, AI applications offer native and target languages at a minimum cost. Digital language learning applications offer interactive and entertaining learning experiences that develop diversity in manner and orientation.

The revolutionary integration of information technology has evolved the instructional techniques of teaching and learning. This modern-day advancement has helped educators develop a mixed curriculum for education. They designed a technology-based curriculum for instructional courses in language. Artificial Intelligence has enabled traditional setups to develop individualised, effective, and easy-to-access learning environments (Muhammad et al., 2025a). Research has expressed different aspects where improvement can be witnessed through artificial intelligence (Elearning, 2025).

First, the AI analyses the recordings and provides a judgment. This feature enables us to design personalised learning experiences for individual evaluation. AI-powered systems customise learning tracks, materials, and learning speed according to the particular needs of the student (Owoc et al., 2021). Second, artificial intelligence uses automatic response systems and provides repetitive tasks to facilitate educators' focus on more complex tasks. Third, AI analyses the current score and suggests the next stage content according to the learner's capacity. Lastly, artificial intelligence helps educators transform their pedagogical methods by providing a quick evaluation of learners' performance (Owoc et al., 2021).

Artificial intelligence has the potential to reintegrate language learning environments, particularly in spoken communication (Qiao & Zhao, 2023). The purpose of artificial intelligence is to create a virtual learning environment that reduces students' anxiety and boredom in a physical classroom (Bai, 2025; Fang, 2025; Nhan et al., 2025). Additionally, AI has proven that students become enthusiastic during interactive language learning courses, and materials are designed according to the level of learners' capacity. AI can customise learning content

after analysing a few questions asked of the learners.

In physical classes, there is a sense of hesitation and fear of judgment by peers and teachers. However, artificial intelligence works in the opposite manner. AI helps rectify mistakes without personal or prejudiced opinions. AI possesses the capacity equal to the comprehension of a physical mentor in evaluating or understanding the speech of students (Abdallah, 2025). This capacity helps when the availability of native speakers is difficult to evaluate, rectify, and polish the speaking skills of learners. It is appropriate to admit that AI applications are highly auspicious in this domain.

Owing to artificial intelligence, learners can now have improved programs to learn better pronunciation with fluency. AI applications such as chatbots, Talk Pal, and Elsa Speak, and many others with speech recognition software provide customised and reality-based feedback to test takers (Dikaprio & Dahlan Diem, 2024).

Human examiners manually analyse outcomes using a predetermined criterion. These methods have some shortcomings in terms of their scales and objectives. Test evaluation may provide subjective bias and unjust judgments. Traditional assessment is not dependable or purposeful because scoring procedures can be judgmental (Avant, 2025). Contextual domains are sometimes ignored in conventional assessment methods, but they are effective for better interaction.

Artificial intelligence has replaced this system by using radical technologies, language assessment, e-learning, and natural language processing (Oopen, 2023). Artificial intelligence generates standard results and develops a new path to polish speaking skills. SmallTalk2, Talk Pal, Elsa Speak, Rosetta Stone, and a few other applications can serve as validated instruments to assess a person's speaking capacity (Manggiasih et al., 2023). Such AI-supported speaking assistance stores

voice recordings

and analyses them without personal opinion.

Automated processes are currently used for monitoring. These applications use natural language processing techniques to understand and analyse spoken skills (Manggiasih et al., 2023). Artificial intelligence analyses the syntax, vocabulary, interaction, and fluency of users. Recordings of speakers are analysed using reference models, which may track areas of improvement. The artificial intelligence systems create comments and suggestions in response.

AI-based applications can also be tailored to educational tools. Such algorithms will be able to identify the areas of weakness of the learners and create the necessary exercise material to eliminate these gaps in their speaking skills (Abdallah, 2025). A learner-centred style fosters confidence, exposure, and minimises anxiety.

The use of technology in language learning has become radical, wherein language learning software is used on e-learning platforms that facilitate distance learning. Among the latest inventions in this sphere is the application of Artificial Intelligence in learning languages. AI can tremendously improve the quality of English language learning by offering more customised and adaptive learning to attain learning goals (Claned, 2024). This technology enables the analysis of the individual needs and abilities of students, real-time feedback, and adaptation of learning materials based on the progress of students. Pragmatism, reliability, validity, and authenticity should be adhered to. Therefore, the dependency on applications cannot be carried out blindly. A significant goal should be to understand AI-based assessments.

The skill of speaking the English language has been enhanced through an application named Talkpal AI, which was created to enhance AI-based applications. The app is based on speech recognition and natural

language processing technologies to replicate conversations and provide users with real-time feedback (Dikaprio & Dahlan Diem, 2024). Using TalkPal AI, the user has the opportunity to receive a more engaging and customisable learning experience, by means of which the user can train based on personal requirements and capabilities.

Additionally, the app's ability to provide immediate feedback and tailor learning materials to individual needs makes it a potential tool for improving English speaking skills. It facilitates the design of better content for speaking practice than conventional classroom practice. Personalised learning theory through artificial intelligence is particularly pertinent and valued. The CHAT-Acts framework was proposed by Lin and Chang. It highlights that artificial intelligence supports individualised and active language learning along with attributes of goal setting, progress follow-up, and imperative feedback. These attributes are highly valuable for academic and professional communication (Abdallah, 2025).

Research Objectives

The current study was conducted to review current practices and outline a framework for an AI-based speaking module for students. In particular, this study has the following objective:

To evaluate the effect of AI on the speaking proficiency of learners of the English language

Significance of the Study

One of the basic and inevitable factors motivating this study stems from the emerging trends of artificial intelligence related to customised learning experiences according to individual learners' needs. In contrast, tech-deprived classrooms follow a uniform approach to instruction. The significance lies in the capacity to facilitate application developers, educators,

policymakers, and other stakeholders in designing the best variants. By analysing strengths and weaknesses, this study assesses the level of impact of AI tools and provides suggestions for teaching methodologies and student involvement.

Literature Review

Artificial intelligence has the capacity to change the way teaching and learning have been performed in schools in the past. In particular, AI can have a tremendous impact on the speaking and listening skills of English Language learners. AI has proven to be an influential means of learning in the field of language. One significant application of AI is customised education and objective evaluation (Elearning, 2025).

Artificial intelligence (AI) devices may be tailored based on needs, backgrounds, culture, and the content of curriculum. Such algorithms are able to identify the weak areas of the learners and generate the necessary practise materials to address the area of weaknesses in speaking skills. This is a student-centred strategy, which boosts confidence, improves exposure, and decreases anxiety (Abdallah, 2025).

According to research, articulation, pronunciation, fluency, and accuracy have been improved through these tools (Kristiawan et al., 2024). Personalised and non-judgmental feedback makes it easier for the learner to repeat the same mistake and receive better suggestions (Claned, 2024). Error repetition does not block the way to motivation for learning. AI-supported applications provide day-to-day practice for effective language learning in a natural environment (Wu, 2024), with ease and comfort. These applications make it feasible to practice real-life situations. This helps boost confidence and enhance the level of expertise.

Self-monitoring of AI algorithms helps design customised content for learners to speed up their fluency. AI-generated suggestions, design modules, and practice exercises. These exercises highlight the weak areas of utterances and suggest practising accurate phonetic corrections. AI-based applications are designed according to the native accent of the English Language.

According to a meta-analysis by Wu (2024), the influence of AI tools has significantly improved language learning with unbiased and free-of-personal-prejudices practices. AI tools, such as chatbots, Elsa speak, and Duolingo, have been proven to be highly effective in different studies. According to a study by Yuan (2023), EFL classroom learners at a Chinese elementary school showed tremendous improvement in oral English skills, and they were willing to practice this application rather than the conventional method to develop better speaking skills. They used it for three months, and the learner-centred approach to error identification created a friendly and easy-to-use learning environment.

EFL students are excited to incorporate AI tools in their studies because AI intervention creates a stress-free environment to converse without fear of being tagged as incompetent at any stage of learning. Pronunciation with Voice Recognition Systems was observed in a study (Nguyen et al., 2025). Awareness of mistakes and the passion to correct them have different perspectives while using these applications. The incorporation of artificial intelligence tools in language learning promotes learner autonomy and reduces anxiety. It was pointed out that AI-powered tools such as ChatGPT can provide immediate and personalised feedback, whereby learners can identify errors and specify matters to work on. Such a personality approach can help not only provide learners with better speaking skills but also motivate them and bring them more confidence.

AI Tools and Real-time Feedback

One of the key aspects of AI language learning platforms is their capacity to provide instant feedback, which the classroom environment usually fails to provide because of the scarcity of teachers and a high number of students in the classroom (Lu et al., 2025). Max and Maffett (2015) emphasised that oral feedback is less effective when delayed, but the AI speech recognition technology provides the opportunity to identify the mistakes of pronunciation immediately. This immediacy assists in establishing a trial-and-error learning environment whereby students are able to learn how to correct themselves and strengthen correct production.

It is also important to realise individualisation of feedback. With the help of such tools as Elsa Speak or Talkpal that recognise where the fluent has a lot of mispronunciations or some other fluent shortcomings, one can give feedback depending on the requirements of the fluent. As May et al. (2025) revealed, students who used AI pronunciation tutors were provided with specific instructions that focused on personal challenges to make recorded improvements in oral accuracy. This individualised system can be associated with the concepts of differentiated instruction, as learning becomes more inclusive and efficient.

Another benefit of AI feedback is that it improves the development of fluency by monitoring prosody, rhythm, and rate of speech pacing. Binhammad et al. (2024) reported that chatbot-based learning environments not only corrected errors but also encouraged extended responses in real-time dialogue, which improved learners' ability to maintain conversation flow. By simulating authentic communication scenarios, AI agents reduce anxiety and promote confidence, allowing learners to practice without the fear of judgment.

Challenges and Limitations

The education system does not focus on students in the long term to achieve the definite goals of language learning, particularly in the speaking aspect. Written content in exams is being evaluated even in linguistics competency courses. There is no evaluation at the end of language courses or any language subject to determine whether the student has become proficient in speaking. Therefore, students do not weigh learning from AI along with other preparations for the exam.

Academic factors are ignored when using artificial intelligence tools for language practice. Curriculum was the least concerned area of AI involvement. The content in AI tools is not being created according to the age and courses they are enrolled in. There is also a gap between academic degrees and professional requirements. However, language capacity is always assessed at the end of an academic career. All professions expect language fluency and accuracy, but students do not find suitable practice for job interviews and presentations to excel in their relevant fields.

Cultural sensitivity has also been ignored. For instance, designed practices follow European and American cultures, along with their accents. This creates obstacles to learning for students. Cultural sensitivity and cross-cultural empathy are not part of the practices designed by artificial intelligence. Social communication is always monitored by cultural practices. Therefore, words in the English language and the style of content delivery may affect speaking practice within that particular culture.

After gaining better proficiency, students rely less on and used AI tools occasionally. AI accessibility is mostly used for academic purposes rather than for general communication. Translation and interpretation through artificial intelligence can be misused without verification. For example, medical

guidance, safety

information, and assessment criteria for individual assessments still require human-based verification (Shahmerdanova, 2025).

Artificial intelligence tools are unable to handle classroom interaction due to the absence of humour and sarcasm, and body language and tone can be compromised when a class is managed through an AI application alone (Dimitriadou & Lanitis, 2023). Cloud-based AI tools often require high-speed Internet. Most schools do not provide reliable Internet access. Developing countries cannot provide Internet facilities and paid access to artificial intelligence tools for students and teachers.

Data privacy is also a serious concern if personal data are used through artificial intelligence tools. Data protection procedures should be strictly monitored by teachers and administrators (Shahriar et al., 2023). Human cognition should be supported by AI tools but AI should not hinder or replace the mental practice of cognition (Abdallah, 2025).

Teacher's Role in AI-based Learning

Teachers play a key role in the smooth collaboration between AI tools and pedagogical methods. This complex process presents both opportunities and challenges. Learning does not only deal with grammatical complexity. It is also authentic linguistic experiences are that which originate out of the interaction of human beings. Educators are the professionals and they are skilled in creating a balanced pedagogic plan with the assistance of AI. Linguistic thought process is debatable; thought process is not simply the correction of the errors; it is an issue of contextual knowledge and other intricate language processes.

The contextual background and feedback mechanisms have a significant role in the retention and engagement in language acquisition (Ramadan Elbaoui Shaddad & Jember, 2024). There, feedback process instantiates language structure which gives

more assurance to the learners, which gives them an opportunity to be active participants on activities governed by situations.

Research Methodology

We intended to study the issues of the introduction of artificial intelligence into language learning and its impact on speaking skills and, according to this purpose, the research design, data collection methods, participants, tools, data analysis, and ethical considerations are presented in the following section.

Research Design

Quantitative research design was used to provide responses to the research questions in their entirety. It was a research that used the experimental study to investigate how artificial intelligence tools affected the speaking of English language learners (Edmonds & Kennedy, 2017; Fraenkel et al., 2012; Mills & Gay, 2019). It gives a detailed insight into the complicated interdependence between the views of artificial intelligence and learning a language. The several impacts of the integration of artificial intelligence into the language learning were investigated using a quantitative method (Grix, 2019).

The experimental group had pre-test and post-test. Respondents were selected randomly into the control group that applied traditional speaking instruction patterns without the use of AI tools, and the experimental category that followed where AI was used to aid the instructions. This intervention will allow drawing a parallel between the outcomes of applying AI and conventional methods.

The research problem was understood through the collection of quantitative data (Salkind, 2017). The collected results were used. A direct comparison of the two datasets yields the data sources (Leedy & Ormrod, 2015). The findings can be generalised because of the quantitative data. Quantitative data were gathered to address the study's research

topics. Because formative evaluation typically takes a month to complete, the study lasted four weeks. For the quantitative phase of the study, the participants in the groups were required to complete tasks related to AI-based platforms each week on an AI-based application, TalkPal. The dependent variable (DV) in this study was speaking proficiency, and the independent variable (IV) was the impact of artificial intelligence.

Participants and Sampling

One hundred and twenty female upper-secondary English language learners participated in the study. The task of evaluating language learners' performance and assisting them during the intervention period fell to the language teacher. Students who received English instruction at the upper secondary level comprised the study population. Using a straightforward random sampling technique, students from six distinct colleges were chosen as the sample.

Experimental Group (n = 60): Practiced speaking exercises on TalkPal

Control Group (n = 60): Practiced speaking exercises in traditional classroom settings.

They were questioned at the beginning of the process regarding their knowledge of AI applications. Those who responded positively to the question were specifically chosen to use AI-enabled language learning resources. The 120 participants chosen ranged in age from 16 to 20 years. As previously mentioned, the selected participants had an intermediate educational background. All chosen participants were assembled in a physical classroom once a week to get answers to their questions regarding the TalkPal AI App.

Instruments and Intervention Procedure

A standardised English-speaking test on the AI-based web browser smalltalk2.me was used before and after the intervention to assess speaking descriptors, such as fluency, pronunciation, grammar, vocabulary, and

interaction. A CEFR-aligned rubric was used to score the speaking performance. The intervention lasted for six weeks.

The group used AI tools such as TalkPal for 30 minutes daily with Emma (AI-based tutor), three times per week. These tools provide automated, real-time feedback on learners' speaking performance, focusing on pronunciation, fluency, and language use.

The control group received conventional English instruction, which included teacher-led discussions, pair work, and oral presentations without AI integration.

Data Collection Procedure

Before the experiment, a carefully designed AI-based pretest was used, and a similar test was used after the experiment. Students were evaluated based on a variety of fluency, grammar, vocabulary, pronunciation, and interaction criteria. All tests were conducted using Smalltalk2 and recorded for later examination.

Language teachers observed the learners' performances throughout the intervention period, and digital learning graphs of the TalkPal App were employed to observe the language learners' performances indirectly. Language instructors watched the students' performances, and digital graphs were utilised to monitor the students' performances in a more indirect way.

Additionally, the performance of the language learners was encoded in the dataset. The language teacher observed learning graphs while the selected participants performed tasks. The results obtained through the pretest were compared with the results of the post-test, and the results of language learning were compared between the control group and the experimental group based on the evaluation and assessment standards that Smalltalk2 offers. AI-integrated platforms were used to gather language proficiency scores, which were then compared with conventional language learning techniques. Metrics of user

involvement, such as job completion rates and task duration, were obtained from Talk Pal.

Data Analysis Procedure

The data were analysed using IBM SPSS Statistics. Descriptive statistics: The results before and after administering the tests to the two groups were compared to determine the means and standard deviations. A paired-samples t-test was used to determine the importance of improvement in each group from the pre- to post-test (Field, 2024). The post-test outcomes of the experimental and control groups were compared using an independent samples t-test. Cohen's effect size, d or Cohen, is a measure that is adopted to determine the usefulness of an intervention. The level of significance for all results was set at .05.

Validity and Reliability

The rubric and the speaking test were professionally checked, and content validity was provided in terms of the international standards of language proficiency (the CEFR of Reference of Languages). Against this was consistency which involved the use of similar data collection procedures.

Ethical Considerations

The critical ethical issues in the course of the study were important. All the participants were informed consent participants, and their names were anonymised so that they were anonymised (Ryen, 2021). The study did not impose any restrictions on the participants, who were at liberty to terminate the study at any time and data privacy and confidentiality were observed. The present research provides a highly comprehensive research on the application of AI in language learning as a mixed research study (Iphofen & Tolich, 2018). This article assists in understating the influence of AI on language learning. It examines linguistic abilities, individualisation, cultural approach and ethics and quantitative data are used in the study for this purpose. The article adheres to the ethical

standards set by American Psychological Association (APA, 2020).

Results

The statistical test results are presented in the following section. The tests included an evaluation of the effect of treatment on the speaking skills of the students. A number of statistical tests were utilised in the study. These were descriptive statistics, paired sample t-tests and independent sample t-tests. It also relied on treatment effect tests, effect sizes tests and mixed design ANOVA. These were the tests which guaranteed proper results.

Descriptive Statistics

The means and standard deviations are presented in Table 1. It shows the information on all variables and the information is derived during pre-tests and post-tests for both control and experimental groups.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Control Pre (M)	Control Pre (SD)	Control Post (M)	Control Post (SD)	Experimental Pre (M)	Experimental Pre (SD)	Experimental Post (M)	Experimental Post (SD)
Fluency	16.76	6.77	15.16	1.66	17.65	13.76	19.70	9.44
Grammar	15.67	9.23	14.33	8.71	17.13	19.09	19.21	13.29

Pronunciation	15.71	10.50	18.00	7.00	16.67	15.54	18.17	9.76
Interaction	16.05	2.13	15.30	0.38	16.50	13.07	18.67	9.38
Vocabulary	14.98	1.17	14.83	7.83	14.79	13.42	16.00	10.78
Overall Speaking	15.83	7.50	17.66	7.60	17.03	11.64	18.33	7.33

Paired Sample Tests

Comparisons between pre- and post-test scores were performed using paired-sample t-tests for each group.

Table 2: Control Group

Variable	t	df	p
Fluency	8.01	59	< .001
Grammar	7.13	59	< .001
Pronunciation	7.82	59	< .001
Interaction	7.88	59	< .001
Vocabulary	7.76	59	< .001
Overall Speaking Score	12.50	59	< .001

Table 3: Experimental Group:

Variable	T	df	p
Fluency	-15.90	59	< .001
Grammar	-9.91	59	< .001
Pronunciation	-9.60	59	< .001
Interaction	-16.49	59	< .001
Vocabulary	-7.30	59	< .001

Overall Speaking Score	-13.95	59	< .001
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The control group reported a considerable decline in all speaking components between the pre- and post-tests. Conversely, the experimental group performed well on all measures.

Independent-Sample T-tests

Independent-sample t-tests were used to compare the experimental factors with the control factors in the pre- and post-tests.

Table 4: Independent-Sample T-Tests

Variable	Test	t	df	P
Fluency	Pre-test	-4.50	118	< .001
Fluency	Post-test	20.57	118	< .001
Grammar	Pre-test	-7.47	118	< .001
Grammar	Post-test	24.30	118	< .001
Pronunciation	Pre-test	-3.62	118	< .001
Pronunciation	Post-test	20.95	118	< .001
Interaction	Pre-test	-2.17	118	0.032
Interaction	Post-test	17.14	118	< .001
Vocabulary	Pre-test	0.92	118	0.359
Vocabulary	Post-test	12.50	118	< .001
Overall Speaking Score	Pre-test	-7.09	118	< .001
Overall Speaking Score	Post-test	29.46	118	< .001

All speaking components in the post-test also showed significant differences between the control and experiment groups (all p < .001), where the experimental group performed better. The majority of components

demonstrated significant differences, except for vocabulary in the pre-test (p = 0.359).

Treatment Effect with Effect Sizes

Cohen's d was calculated to assess the magnitude of treatment effects.

Table 5: Treatment Effect Sizes

Variable	t	Df	p	Cohen's d
Fluency	-20.57	118	< .001	-3.76
Grammar	-24.30	118	< .001	-4.44
Pronunciation	-20.95	118	< .001	-3.82
Interaction	-17.14	118	< .001	-3.13
Vocabulary	-12.50	118	< .001	-2.28
Overall Speaking Score	-29.46	118	< .001	-5.38

Cohen's d was calculated to determine the strength of the treatment effects.

Multiple Comparisons with Bonferroni Correction

To adjust the Type I error in numerous comparisons, the Bonferroni correction was used. The adjusted level of significance was p = .008 (.05/6), considering six variables.

Post-test differences between experimental and control population groups were all statistically significant with Bonferroni correction, employing the results to prove their strength.

Mixed-Design ANOVA

A mixed-design ANOVA of 2 × 2 was used: time (pre-test vs. post-test) was a within-subject variable, and group (control vs. experimental) was a between-subjects variable.

Table 6: Mixed ANOVA for Overall Speaking Score

Effect	SS	df	F	p
C(Group)	41870.42	1	560.01	<.001
C(Time)	570.42	1	7.63	0.006
C(Group):C(Time)	11620.42	1	155.42	<.001
Residual	17645.00	23	-	-

For overall speaking score, there was a significant main effect of group ($p < .001$), a significant main effect of time ($p = 0.006$), and a significant group \times time interaction ($p < .001$). This indicates that the experimental group improved significantly more from pre-test to post-test compared to the control group.

Discussion

Interpretation of Descriptive and Inferential Analyses

The descriptive statistics showed different trends of changes in speaking proficiency between the experimental and control groups. There was a decreasing trend in all speaking components of the control group compared to the pre- and post-tests, but an appreciable improvement in all speaking components in the experimental group. These opposing trends indicate that conventional training might not be adequate to retain or enhance speaking prowess compared to AI-mediated training, which offers proficient scaffolding for skill growth.

Interpretation of Inferential Analyses

The paired t-tests ensured that the differences between each group were statistically significant. The deterioration of the control group could be explained by insufficient practice opportunities, absence of personal feedback, and potential anxiety related to test-taking in a traditional classroom environment. On the other hand, the observation of the positive growth of the experimental group on

all levels, such as

fluency, grammar, pronunciation, interaction, and vocabulary, is an indication of the overall positive effects of the AI tools.

The Independent sample t-tests showed that there were significant differences between the pre-and post-intervention of the groups that were very significant, and the experimental group had a higher performance compared to the control group. The findings are consistent with the past studies that state that AI-based applications offer prompt personalised feedback that leads to faster language acquisition (Zhang et al., 2024).

Multiple Comparisons with Bonferroni Correction

The evidence that all the comparisons were significant following Bonferroni correction will help boost confidence in the research findings and minimise the chances of the results being due to randomness. This kind of strength is of particular necessity given the many dimensions of speaking proficiency being measured.

Theoretical and Pedagogical Implications

The findings support the personalised learning theory that presupposes that the type of instructional forms that are oriented to the individual learner needs enhance the outcomes. Some of these tools are in AI such as TalkPal that assists a learner to adapt to performance, provides instant feedback to them, as well as gives them an opportunity to practise without any form of stigma and judgement.

The CHAT-Acts framework developed by Lin and Chang (2023) is concerned with the specific features of effective learning with the help of AI, which include goal setting, progress monitoring, and imperative feedback. This model is confirmed by the findings of the current research and demonstrates that AI tools can apply these principles in the area of speaking education.

These findings have pedagogic implications, indicating that AI technologies can be

introduced into language curriculum in order to supplement traditional instruction. The teachers will also have an opportunity to work with AI in personalised practise and assessment and consequently spend some time in the classroom on other components of higher-order communication, cultural conversation and human interaction which cannot be replicated by the AI. Nevertheless, to ensure the effective usage of AI tools by learners and overcome such limitations as cultural sensitivity and contextual relevance, teacher guidance is also required (Athar et al., 2025).

Another issue identified in this study is the need to minimise affective barriers to speaking practice. Devices are used by AI to achieve anxiety-free learning, in which learners can feel free to explore the language without the fear of being judged negatively (Fathi et al., 2024; Huong, 2025). This kind of psychological safety is essential for building speaking confidence and fluency.

However, despite the overwhelming positive effects, several limitations should be noted. This was a relatively short study (six weeks) on a particular population (female higher secondary students in Pakistan). Such effects are expected to be established by longitudinal research using more heterogeneous populations to validate them. Moreover, even though AI tools can be highly beneficial in offering technical feedback about accent, grammar, and fluency, one may say that they do not have the capacity to emphasise pragmatic competence, cultural nuances, and negotiable and spontaneous speech of humans.

Conclusion

The article examined the effect of AI tools, which, in this case, are the TalkPal AI, on the speaking skills of higher secondary level English learners. The results suggest that AI-based teaching generates the speaking skill of the students of much higher quality in all

speaking proficiency areas in regard to fluency, grammar, pronunciation, interaction, and vocabulary as compared to teaching in the classroom environment. These are viable improvements with regard to large effect sizes, as well as, robust statistical outcomes.

Implications of the Study

These findings have implications on the policy and practise of international language education. AI speech assistance software should be incorporated into the curriculum of learning institutions to make sure that learners can afford to practise affordably at a personal level. Through the teacher training educational programmes, teachers must be provided with the means of efficiently incorporating these technologies into their pedagogic practise since they may and must supplement but not replace human lessons.

To the application developers, the given study provides an indication of the importance of designing contextually appropriate and culturally relevant content that aligns with the currency standards and needs of the learners. Cooperation between teachers, scientists, and technology providers is the best way to ensure that AI instruments are pedagogically and ethically sound.

One of the problems that policymakers must tackle is the issue of infrastructure, especially in developing nations, by investing in stable Internet connections and ensuring that AI tools are affordable and accessible to everyone who learns. Priorities should be on data privacy and ethical issues to safeguard learner data and make AI use in education responsible.

Limitations of the Study

Some limitations should be mentioned. First, the research was conducted among students of a particular geographic area and exclusively among female students, which can restrict generalisability. Second, the retention of gains and maintenance may not be exhibited due to

the six-week intervention, which shows significant effects only. Third, this study did not analyse the particularities of learner traits (e.g. motivation, previous experience with technologies) that could mediate the outcome of the AI tools. Fourth, although AI tools presented technical feedback, pragmatic competence and sociolinguistic appropriateness were not thoroughly evaluated.

Recommendations for Future Research

These limitations can be overcome in future research by using several approaches. Other longitudinal studies examining the effects of AI on learners over the long term would help understand the sustainability of AI-mediated improvements and the best usage frequencies. Generalisability would be improved by using various populations in various educational contexts, age groups, and levels of proficiency.

Comparative research exploring the various AI tools and their peculiar features would assist in determining the best practices for design and implementation. A qualitative analysis of user experience and pedagogical integration through mixed-methods research, including qualitative data collected by the participants (learners and teachers), would be much deeper.

Lastly, studies on adapting AI tools in a cultural context and implementing them in a variety of languages and cultures would be crucial in solving the much-needed equity issue. Responsible innovation would also be encouraged through scrupulous enquiry on privacy-safe technologies and ethical principles on the application of AI in learning environments.

The current study adds to the increasing literature suggesting that AI tools may have a tremendous impact on language learning. With the further development of these technologies, it will be necessary to conduct new studies and consider their application to

gain the most advantages and reduce drawbacks and moral aspects. AI inclusion in language learning can be implemented as a companion rather than a substitution of human instruction and can effectively multiply access, personalise education, and fast-track skills acquisition among English language learners.

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